

Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography as a tool for targeted and non-targeted analysis of contaminants of emerging concern in wastewater

Jason Devers^{*}, David I. Pattison, Asger B. Hansen, Jan H. Christensen

Analytical Chemistry Group, Department of Plant and Environmental Science, Faculty of Science, University of Copenhagen, 1871, Frederiksberg C, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Wastewater
GC×GC
Non-targeted analysis
Derivatization

ABSTRACT

Wastewater is a major reservoir for chemical contaminants, both anthropogenic and biogenic. Recent chemical and toxicological analysis reveals the abundance and impact of these compounds, often termed contaminants of emerging concern (CECs). Concurrently, incomplete removal of these compounds in wastewater treatment plants sets a precedent for detailed characterisation and monitoring of such substances. Although liquid chromatography (LC) is frequently used for analysis of CECs in wastewater, gas chromatography (GC) maintains its significance for non-polar to mid-polar analytes. GC offers advantages such as increased separation efficiency, fewer matrix effects, and greater availability and reliability of reference mass spectra compared to LC. Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography (GC × GC) delivers unmatched peak capacity and separational capabilities, critical in the resolution of diverse compound groups present within wastewater. When coupled with high resolution mass spectrometry, it provides a powerful identification tool with spectral databases and both 1st and 2nd dimensional retention indices, and has allowed for the separation, reliable annotation and characterisation of diverse CECs within wastewater in recent years. Herein, on the basis of recent studies from the last fifteen years, we outline cutting-edge methodologies and strategies for wastewater analysis using GC × GC. This includes sample preparation, derivatization of polar analytes, instrumental setup, and data analysis, ultimately providing the reader a framework for future non-targeted analysis of wastewater and other complex environmental matrices.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been increasing concern about the ubiquitous presence of chemical contaminants in the environment, both from natural and anthropogenic sources [1].

In the context of wastewater, toxicological analysis of wastewater samples has shown that only 1–5% of the measurable toxicity can be attributed to currently monitored compounds (via experiments referred to as iceberg experiments) [2–4]. This highlights a significant knowledge gap in the current understanding of toxic contaminants in wastewater, and provides an onus to monitor and reduce these unmonitored components in the interest of environmental and human health.

Many terms can be found in the literature to categorise these unmonitored compounds, such as contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) described by Dulio et al. (2019) as “chemicals that are currently not regulated (not submitted to a routine monitoring and/or emission

control regime), but may be under scrutiny for future regulation.” [5]. Smital et al. (2008) describe emerging contaminants (ECs) as “any synthetic or naturally occurring chemical or any microorganism that is not commonly monitored in the environment, but has the potential to enter the environment and cause known or suspected adverse ecological and/or human health effects.” [6]. Emerging pollutants (EPs) are defined by the United States Environmental Protection Agency as “new chemicals without regulatory status and which impact on environment and human health are poorly understood” [7]. Kümmerer (2011), however, critiques the use of these terms for their lack of a concrete definition and their opportunity to be openly interpreted. Instead, he suggests the use of the term micro-pollutant, which he defines as “compounds present in the environment in the $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$ range and below, independently of their chemical structure, usage or mode of action.” [8].

Due to the incomplete removal efficiency of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) for eliminating CECs, WWTPs serve as a major pathway

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: jpd@plen.ku.dk (J. Devers), dip@plen.ku.dk (D.I. Pattison), asgerbh@plen.ku.dk (A.B. Hansen), jch@plen.ku.dk (J.H. Christensen).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2024.127032>

Received 17 June 2024; Received in revised form 7 October 2024; Accepted 9 October 2024

Available online 10 October 2024

0039-9140/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

for the introduction of CECs into surface water [1]. This has been shown to potentially affect aquatic organisms, threaten the sustainability of aquatic ecosystems, and pose risks to human health [9]. Contamination of drinking water reserves with CECs has also been reported [10,11].

Within the broad category of CECs, many subcategories/groups of compounds can be found, categorized by either source, common use, or chemical properties. These include but are not limited to, PAHs (Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons), POPs (Persistent Organic Pollutants), VOCs (Volatile Organic Compounds) [12], EDCs (Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals), PPCPs/PCPs (Personal Care Products, pharmaceuticals [13]) and PMTs (Persistent, Mobile and Toxic) [14].

Due to their inherent polarity and mobility, PMTs present a hazard to drinking water sources by penetrating riverbanks and barriers in WWTPs. This can result in breakthroughs in drinking water treatment facilities, posing risks to public health [14].

Less persistent CECs are also a concern as they are consistently detected in environmental samples such as wastewater, owing to their continuous use and discharge [15].

The wide range of chemical properties presents a significant analytical challenge in separating and identifying all contaminants. Typically, a combination of techniques, including gas and liquid chromatography, is employed for comprehensive compound screening in wastewater [16].

Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC-MS) is commonly preferred for the analysis of organic compounds in aqueous samples, especially polar and thermally labile contaminants, as opposed to gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) [17]. LC-MS has been used extensively in the analysis of polar CECs in water samples, for example, the analysis of PPCPs in wastewater by Malvar et al. (2019) [18], persistent micropollutants and transformation products by Tisler et al. (2022) [19] and the non-targeted identification of 590 CECs in river and wastewater by Mechelke et al. (2019) [20].

GC-MS fills an important niche in the analysis of non-polar CECs and is often used in conjunction with LC-MS to carry out a more thorough screening of CECs in wastewater samples. For example, using GC-MS in the analysis of fractionated mid-polar and non-polar extracts of wastewater, and LC-MS for the analysis of the polar extract [21]. In addition to this application range, GC-MS offers many benefits over LC-MS such as higher separation efficiency, lower operational costs, and fewer issues related to matrix effects [17], as demonstrated in the analysis of pharmaceutical residues in complex environmental matrices [22].

Additionally, early standardisation of the ionisation energy used in GC-MS has meant that over several decades large reference databases of mass spectra are available for the tentative identification of unknown compounds [23], with the NIST and Wiley 2023 libraries now containing over 394 and 873 thousand spectra [24,25]. Electron ionization mass spectra in GC-MS are highly fragmented, with fragments allowing for structural elucidation, giving each compound a reproducible fingerprint, a significant advantage over liquid chromatography mass spectrometry with electrospray ionization [26]. Further confidence in these tentative identifications can also be gained using reference retention indices (available within spectral libraries such as NIST), which compare the relative retention of compounds to a series of standards [27]. The combination of these two approaches has become standardised in the identification of unknown compounds in GC-MS, as they are largely independent of the instrument and chromatographic conditions, and hence are readily applicable across different laboratories. Additionally, standardised methods for communicating the certainty of tentative identifications have been developed using these tools, which will be detailed in a later section (Annotation of non-target features) [28,29].

While analysis using both GC and LC covers a wide range of analytes, spanning 8 orders of magnitude (D_{OW} values), many polar analytes, particularly those with negative $\log D_{OW}$ values are not suitable for either platform [30]. Coupled with the observation that the polar fraction of fractionated wastewater extracts carries the majority of measurable

toxic effects, there is an onus on the analysis of more polar compounds [31]. Hydrophilic interaction LC (HILIC) and supercritical fluid chromatography (SFC) allow for the analysis of these compounds and both techniques have been gaining traction in the analysis of more polar contaminants in recent years [30]. Derivatization expands the polarity range of GC [32], which will be discussed in a later section.

Since the 1990s, technological advancements in GC have greatly expanded its application range. In particular, the introduction of comprehensive two-dimensional GC (GC \times GC) in 1991 [33] expanded chromatographic separation using two separate interactions (typically non-polar in the 1st dimension, and more polar in the 2nd), increasing polarity coverage and peak capacity compared to conventional one-dimensional GC [34]. Two orthogonal separation mechanisms produce structured chromatograms when homologous series of compounds are contained in the sample [35], with compound groups eluting in discreet bands within the two dimensional separation space. This aids qualitative comparisons of samples [36], facilitates identification by proximity to related compounds [37], and enables more accurate quantification compared to conventional GC-MS by separating matrix components from targets [38]. The separation of more polar analytes with GC \times GC offers an interesting opportunity for the analysis of more polar CECs, such as PMTs in wastewater. Over the past decade, significant progress has been made in this area, particularly in regards to non-targeted analysis [37,39]. Furthermore, the addition of a second dimension can allow for more confident identification of unknowns through the use of retention indices in the second dimension [40–42]. While determination of second dimension retention indices is still uncommon, due to the complex nature of their determination and the necessity of carrying out multiple additional injections, recent years have yielded simple methods for their determination requiring just one injection of a standard solution [40,41]. Finally, sensitivity is typically heightened due to peak focusing/compression during modulation, thus reducing detection limits for trace contaminants [43,44].

In this review, we will discuss, on the basis of publications spanning the last 15 years, the applicability of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography in the targeted and non-targeted analysis of CECs in wastewater, as well as outlining effective strategies from sample preparation to data analysis and interpretation.

2. Modulators

The modulator is the core component within the GC \times GC system, and is responsible for trapping and injecting effluent from the 1st dimension column into the 2nd dimension column, thereby allowing comprehensive separation [35]. The various modulators types utilised in GC \times GC can be categorized into the thermal and valve-based modulators [45].

2.1. Thermal modulators

Thermal modulators typically operate by trapping and focusing analytes eluting from the 1st dimension column at a low temperature, then rapidly remobilising them into the 2nd dimension column at a higher temperature. Thermal modulators were the first modulator type to be developed, initially demonstrated by Liu & Phillips using an in-house resistively heated trap in their seminal demonstration of GC \times GC [33]. They remain the most prevalent modulator in GC \times GC [43, 45]. An advantage of thermal modulators is their direct coupling of the 1st and 2nd dimension columns, resulting in a duty cycle of 1.0 [46]. However, this coupling limits the trapping and remobilisation of the analytes by the modulator's cooling and heating capabilities.

2.2. Cryogenic thermal modulators

Currently, the most popular cryogenic modulator is the quad jet modulator, which uses two cold jets and two hot jets, to trap/focus and

mobilise the analytes, respectively. The dual jet trapping and refocusing not only minimises breakthrough potential but also reduces peak width, enhancing the signal-to-noise ratio and 2nd dimensional peak capacity. Despite the expenses and complexity of cryogenic systems, a liquid nitrogen cold jet at $-190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ effectively traps and focuses volatile analytes down to C3 [45].

2.3. Cryogen-free thermal modulators

To reduce the costly consumption of cryogenics, cryogen free thermal modulators have been developed. One notable example is the ZX-2 loop thermal modulator (ZOEX, USA), which employs a consumable-free closed-cycle refrigerator/heat exchanger to create a two-stage loop modulator. This modulator generates $-90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ continuous cold jet, trapping and focusing eluent from the 1st dimension while modulating C7+ compounds by volatility. A programmable hot jet, reaching temperatures up to $475\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, is used to mobilise eluent bands, for injection onto the 2nd dimension column (ZOEX ZX-2 Technical Specifications, Brochure, 2012). A similar modulator system is also provided by Sep-solve, the INSIGHT-Thermal modulator, with programmable cold jet flow and a revised loop holder design [47]. The Thermal independent modulator developed by Luong et al. [48], and commercialised by J&X Technologies as the solid state modulator (SSM) uses a Peltier element cooled zone for trapping, and two independently controlled heating zones for remobilisation [48]. While being simpler and more affordable in operation compared to cryogenic systems, higher trapping temperatures limit the applicability of these systems for more volatile analytes with listed applicability of the Insight-Thermal from C7 to C50+ [47], ZX-2 (cold jet flow control) C8 to C45 [49] and J&X SSM C5 to C30 [45, 50].

In addition, several novel and minimalistic cryogen free thermal modulators have been developed but not yet commercialised such as the miniaturised single-stage thermal modulator by Jacobs et al. [51], the “Peltier modulator” by Wohlfahrt et al. [52], and the single-stage consumable-free thermal modulator by Muscalu et al. [53].

2.4. Valve-based modulators

Valve-based/flow modulators typically feature a multi-port valve and operate by collecting the 1st dimension column eluate in a sample loop, with excess eluting through a waste port. Re-injection of this sample loop is then carried out by switching the valve and reversing the flow through the sample loop, allowing injection into the 2nd dimension column. While peaks are not focused during flow modulation, sensitivity enhancements are gained due to compression the 1st dimension effluent due to the much higher flow rate generally used in the 2nd dimension [44]. As this is a temperature-independent process for trapping, it allows for the modulation of more volatile compounds (C1+), offering advantage over thermal modulators. However, this comes at the cost of sensitivity, as incomplete sampling with sample redirected to waste, results in a duty cycle of <1.0 , likely posing a challenge for trace analysis. Another disadvantage is that high flow rates are required for appropriate operation, typically $20\text{--}30\text{ ml/min}$ [45]. Valve-based modulators are typically unsuitable for MS detection, unless paired with atmospheric pressure ionization sources, as they operate in vacuum conditions. When combined with MS detection this challenge may be addressed via splitting the flow into the 2nd dimension column, at the cost of sensitivity. This split flow can also be redirected to another detector, allowing for tandem analysis [34,45]. An example of a contemporary commercially available flow modulator, designed for use in GC \times GC is the Sep-solve Insight, referred to as a reverse fill/flush (RFF) modulator.

During the fill mode, eluate from the 1st dimension column is directed into the sample loop, with excess eluate eluted directed into the bleed line. Upon switching to flush mode, the flow is reversed through the sample loop, injecting its contents into the 2nd dimension column.

While current commercially available flow modulators possess a <1 duty cycle when paired with MS detection, due to necessity of flow splitting, differential flow modulation techniques have been addressing the deficit. Dynamic pressure gradient modulation (DPGM) relies on the creation of dynamic pressure differences to focus and transfer analytes from the first dimension (1D) to the second dimension (2D) column, and has been demonstrated to have a 1.0 duty cycle while remaining compatible with TOF-MS detection [54].

2.5. Column choices

To utilise the increased peak capacity inherent to comprehensive GC \times GC analysis, the separation mechanisms used in the 1st and 2nd dimension must be different. This difference is referred to as orthogonality [55]. Orthogonality also allows for group type separation, where structurally related compounds elute within discrete bands [36]. The two most commonly used separation mechanisms are referred to as follows:

Non-Polar \times Polar/Normal Orthogonality. Non-polar, typically dimethylpolysiloxane, predominantly forms the boiling point separation column in 1st dimension, with a more polar column such as polyethylene glycol or phenyl methylpolysiloxane in the 2nd dimension. From the 29 publications reviewed utilising GC \times GC in the analysis of CECs in wastewater, the vast majority (27) use a non-polar \times polar setup with a mid-polar column in the second dimension, which reflects recent reviews of column choices using GC \times GC [56]. An additional advantage of a non-polar \times polar column setup in the context of non-targeted analysis is the wide availability of reference retention indices using “standard” non-polar columns [40].

Polar \times Non-Polar/Reverse Orthogonality. Polar column in 1st dimension, with a non-polar column in 2nd dimension. Mommers & van der Wal (2021) recently reviewed column selection and optimisation, highlighting the efficacy of a polar \times non-Polar setup for analysing polar analytes in less polar matrices [36]. They suggest using the 1st dimension for polar analytes and the 2nd dimension for matrix components. Additionally, for more polar analytes, ionic liquid stationary phases offer variable selectivity and high thermal stability compared to polyethylene glycol phases [36,57].

3. Detectors

Due to the short modulation period in GC \times GC, peak widths typically range from 25 to 500 ms [35]. To reliably quantify these peaks, approximately 10 data points should be taken across each peak. Thus, a detector with an acquisition rate of at least 50hz is recommended, although some groups have successfully used rates as low as 25 Hz [58]. Flame ionization detection (FID) and time-of-flight mass spectrometers (TOF-MS) are the preferred choices for GC \times GC due their suitability for such rapid data acquisition. High resolution TOF-MS offers the added benefit of providing precise molecular ion masses, facilitating compound identification. Orbitrap mass analysers typically acquire at below recommended acquisition rates ($<25\text{ Hz}$), but have been recently utilised in GC \times GC by decreasing resolving power in order to increase the acquisition rate [59].

Vaye et al. (2022) recently published a review discussing the analysis of POPs in environmental samples. In their work, they elaborate on the applications and comparative advantages of various detectors in GC \times GC [60].

3.1. Flame ionization detector (FID)

In the FID, carbon containing compounds are introduced via the capillary column and burned in a H_2 -air flame. This combustion generates ions, which produce a current at the collector, resulting in a measurable signal directly proportional to the amount of carbon compound present. FID was the first detector to be used in GC \times GC [33] and

due to its low cost, large linear/dynamic range, simplicity and robustness, paired with fast acquisition rates up to 500 Hz, FID is a popular choice for GC × GC detection, and the most reliable for quantification [36]. Nevertheless, the FID's inability to provide compound structural information and its relatively poor detection limits diminish its suitability for non-targeted analysis of complex samples, such as wastewater.

3.2. Single quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS)

Single quadrupole mass spectrometers act as a mass filter, allowing a single mass channel at a time to reach the detector as the specified mass range is scanned [60]. Single quadrupole mass spectrometers typically require a reduced mass scan window or operation in single ion monitoring mode in order to achieve sufficiently fast scan rate [35]. Shimadzu in recent years have been developing rapid scanning QMS instruments for use with GC × GC, with their most recent GCMS-QP2050 model achieving scan rates of up to 30,000 u/sec [61].

3.3. Time-of-flight mass spectrometer (TOF-MS)

Time of flight mass spectrometry operates as follows: Ions from the ion source are accelerated within a flight tube by a known electric field, this acceleration results in an ion having a specific kinetic energy based on its charge. The velocity of the ion depends on the mass-to-charge (m/z). The time for the ion to travel through the flight tube is then measured, which is therefore a measure of its m/z [62]. While early TOF instruments typically offered unit mass resolution at the high acquisition rates required for GC × GC, recent years have seen the development of accurate mass high-resolution time-of-flight detectors such as the Agilent 7250B (Agilent, USA), with an acquisition rate of up to 50 Hz and a resolving power of >25,000. In addition, this system utilises a switchable CI/NCI/PCI ion source and can also operate in Q-TOF mode in which MS/MS can be performed (Agilent 7250B Series GC/Q-TOF System Data Sheet). The flexibility and inherent power of GC × GC-TOF-MS in the identification of unknowns lends itself well to the analysis of CECs and water. Leco (LECO Inc., USA), supply all in one Pegasus 4D GC × GC-HRT equipped with a thermal modulator and high resolution TOF-MS capable of acquisition rates up to 200 Hz [63,64].

3.4. Contaminants of emerging concern

Within the broad category of CECs lie several subcategories of compounds, subclassified based on compound origin or toxicological relevance. These subcategories are outlined below, with an overview provided in Table 1.

3.5. Pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCP)

PPCPs are a group of CECs sometimes referred to as “down the drain” products [12]. Examples of PPCPs are analgesics, lipid regulators, synthetic hormones, steroids, fragrances, sun screens, shampoos, dental care products, cosmetics, disinfectants and insect repellents [12,13].

García et al. (2014) investigated the eco-toxicity of 26 PPCPs, concluding that more than half of the studied PPCPs were at least harmful to aquatic organisms, according to the Globally Harmonized System of Classification of toxicity [65].

Pharmaceuticals, part of the PPCP group, enter WWTPs via urban wastewater networks, including hospital effluent, often discharged without extra treatment. WWTPs usually lack the capacity to fully remove complex compounds such as pharmaceuticals, resulting in their presence in WWTP effluent [66].

Comber et al. (2018) investigated pharmaceutical and metabolite removal by UK WWTPs [67] While most substances were largely removed, effluent concentrations of ethinylestradiol, diclofenac, propranolol and fluoxetine exceeded their predicted no-effect

Table 1

Select compound groups of interest, typical water pollutants and emerging contaminants.

Group	Components	Chemical properties	Reference
PPCPs/PCPs (Pharmaceuticals and Personal care products/Personal care products)	Pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, soaps, sunscreens	Widely varied, both polar and non-polar	[16,37,39, 58,68–70, 85–90]
EDCs (Endocrine disrupting chemicals)	Synthetic (Bisphenol A), Natural (eg. Estrone)	Both polar and non-polar organic compounds	[74,86, 91–93]
PMTs (persistent, mobile and toxic)	Wide ranging as defined under REACH	Very polar (water soluble)	[14]
POPs (persistent organic pollutants) PBTs (Persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic)	POPs: Pesticides, PCBs, PAHs, flame retardants, dioxin PBTs: Predominately non-polar, diverse origin	POPs: Predominately non-polar, many halogenated PBTs: log Dow > 4.5,	[16,37,39, 58,70,78, 84,88,90, 92,94–101]

concentrations (PNECs).

The biological activity, stability and water solubility of pharmaceuticals, combined with concerns of their chronic toxicity and effects on aquatic organisms, underscore the need to detect them in WWTP effluent. This is achieved through non-targeted analysis of CECs [13].

GC × GC has allowed the resolution and identification of previously unidentified diclofenac metabolites [68], yielded sub ng/L detection limits in the analysis of diverse pharmaceuticals [39,69], and non-target screening of PPCPs [70,71]. Meza et al. (2020), used both UHPLC-TOFMS and GC × GC-TOFMS to identify 52 primarily pharmaceutical PPCPs in hospital wastewater samples and assess their removal efficiency using a coir fibre based treatment, 26 of the compounds were characterised using GC × GC-TOFMS, with many toxicologically relevant [71].

3.6. Endocrine disrupting compounds: (EDC)

EDCs are a group of often polar natural and synthetic hormones, as well as industrial chemicals such as Bisphenol-A (BPA), Nonylphenols, PCBs and Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins (PCDDs). EDCs are environmental contaminants, which interfere with the function of the endocrine system of animals, with adverse health effects [72,73]. Due to their polarity, trace level analysis via GC often requires derivatization (covered later) [74]. Nonylphenols can be found in the environment as a mixture of isomers arising from the degradation of nonylphenol polyethoxylate surfactants [75]. While conventional 1D GC-MS has allowed for the resolution of 20 nonylphenol components, GC × GC has allowed for the characterization of 102 components, as illustrated by Ieda et al. (2005) [75].

3.7. Persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT)

Another emerging group of CECs are referred to as persistent, mobile and toxic compounds (PMTs) [14,76]. Within Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) regulation, persistence and toxicity are outlined in Annex XIII [14]. A substance is deemed persistent if its degradation half-life exceeds 60 days in marine water or 40 days in fresh or estuarine water. Mobility is determined by the lowest log K_{OC} (organic carbon-water partition coefficient) between pH 4 and pH9. A log K_{OC} <4.0 defines a substance as mobile, and a log K_{OC} <3.0 as very mobile [14]. Examples of priority PMTs within water are 1,4-dioxane, trichloroethene, trichloromethane, 2,4-dinitrophenol, tris(2-chloroethyl)phosphate, 1,2-dichloropropane, trichloroacetic acid, 1,2-dichloroethane, and 1,2-dimethoxyethane [14].

As a result of PMTs' high polarity, WWTPs and subsurface barriers are expected to be ineffective in the removal of PMTs. Due to their high polarity and persistence, PMTs may migrate into raw waters used for drinking water production [17] leading to their breakthrough in drinking water treatment processes. Additionally, their high polarity leads to challenges in their analysis using conventional LC and GC [14], and may require derivatization for trace detection [30].

3.8. Persistent Organic Pollutants (POP) and persistent, Bioaccumulative and Toxic (PBT)

POPs are a group of CECs, including pesticides, flame retardants (e. g., PFAS, PFOS) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) which may accumulate in wastewaters from both agricultural and urban sources. They are characterised by their capacity to bioaccumulate [12]. PCBs, of which there are 209 congeners, can be challenging to resolve and characterize in conventional GC. In contrast, GC \times GC has been shown to reduce co-elutions and to resolve the majority (181) of the 209 congeners in a single chromatographic run [77]. It has been used to quantify PCBs at trace levels (<10 ng/L) in wastewater samples using a selective micro electron capture detector (μ ECD) [78]. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), used in various consumer products like non-stick cookware and waterproofing agents are suspected of toxicity [79]. While LC-MS is widely used for the non-targeted PFAS analysis, more volatile PFAS are not ionisable using typical LC ionization methods and necessitate GC for analysis [80]. However, GC-MS is relatively underutilised, and so far, no applications have been published for PFAS analysis, possibly due to insufficient PFAS spectra in common mass-spectral databases [81].

Persistent, Bioaccumulative and Toxic (PBT) compounds are a group of CECs with significant overlap with POPs. PBTs are defined under REACH as persistent and toxic compounds, with persistency defined as having a log D_{OW} above 4.5 [82]. This log D_{OW} range puts these compounds well within the application range of GC [30], and methodology for detecting these compounds are well established [76].

GC \times GC has been used to great success in the analysis of these compounds. Dimitriou-Christidis et al. employed a targeted/suspect-screening approach using a suspect list compiled by Harold and Muir 2010 [83]. In addition to 59 target compounds, several compounds including PCBs and organochlorine pesticides were frequently detected in Swiss WWTPs [78].

Non-targeted analysis of PBTs using GC \times GC has also been carried out by Blum et al. (2017), to first screen and then prioritise PBTs based on their removal efficiencies in wastewater [84].

3.9. Sample preparation

Due to the varied chemical properties and low concentrations of CECs in wastewater, sample preparation must provide thorough extraction and adequate preconcentration for both targeted and non-targeted analysis. Moreover, a sample preparation method that allows for chemical measurements and toxicological assays using the same extract would be beneficial for water quality assessments (e.g., iceberg experiments) [3]. The following sections detail the most common sample preparation methodologies used in the extraction of CECs in wastewater samples, which are further summarised in Table 2.

3.10. Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE)

LLE, an established technique in analytical chemistry, is commonly used to extract organic analytes from aqueous samples by exploiting their differing solubilities in two immiscible liquids. In LLE, an aqueous sample is mixed with a water-immiscible organic solvent, allowing the analytes to distribute between the phases. The phases are then separated, and if extraction is incomplete, the process can be repeated with fresh organic solvent [102].

Table 2

Table comparing sample preparation methods, with applicable compounds, advantages and disadvantages listed.

Method	Applicable Compounds	Advantages	Disadvantages	Reference
LLE	Tuneable via solvent selection	Simple, repeatable	Requires large volume of solvent	[86,91, 97–99, 111]
SPE/ML-SPE	Tuneable via sorbent selection	Allows for matrix removal, high enrichment factors, low solvent consumption	Laborious, Inconsistent analyte recovery	[16,37,39, 69,74,78, 84,85, 88–90,93, 94,96,100, 101]
SPME	Volatile compounds, tuneable via sorbent selection	Automatable, requires no extraction solvent, robust	Not suitable for non volatile compounds	[107]
SBSE	Predominately non-polar compounds	Automatable, low detection limits, requires no extraction solvent	Sorbent not suitable for more polar compounds	[70,97, 108,112]

LLE has been used in 8 of the reviewed publications using GC \times GC in the analysis of CECs, in both non-targeted and targeted applications, allowing for the analysis of pharmaceuticals [68], 204 resolved alkyl-phenol isomers [91], personal care products, pesticides, carcinogens and EDCs [86]. Several alternative sample preparation techniques have emerged as substitutes for LLE, aiming to reduce organic solvent usage while enhancing analyte recovery and selectivity [17].

3.11. Solid phase extraction (SPE)

SPE is widely used for trace organic contaminants analysis in water samples. It relies on the solutes' affinity for the porous stationary phase, which upon sample loading become retained, and are subsequently eluted. SPE allows for selective sorption and pre-concentration of analytes or interferences, is automatable, and offers more complete and selective extraction when compared to LLE by eliminating unwanted matrix interferences [102]. Most applications in the literature utilise predominately reversed-phase polymeric SPE sorbents like Oasis HLB or Strata-X. For instance, Jover et al. (2009) separated and quantified benzothiazoles, benzotriazoles and benzosulfonamides using GC \times GC for improved accuracy in quantification, resolving compounds co-eluting in 1D GC [94]. However, reversed-phase sorbents are unsuitable for permanently charged or highly acidic/basic compounds, making it necessary to use mixed-mode/ion exchange cartridges [17]. This underscores the importance of using multiple SPE sorbents simultaneously in non-targeted analysis.

3.12. Multi-layer solid phase extraction (ML-SPE)

Trace analysis of CECs in water samples frequently relies on pre-concentration via the use of a single sorbent material, often utilising hydrophobic interactions. This is followed by analysis using GC or reversed phase LC, both of which typically carry out separation via non-polar interactions. The suitability of this combination of sample preparation and analytical separation has limited suitability to highly polar compounds, such as PMTs as well as acidic/basic compounds which are of interest in screening within wastewater [20].

To tackle this limitation, several groups have assembled multi-layered SPE cartridges, comprised of multiple sorbents with varying selectivities. For example, Mechelke et al. developed a ML-SPE cartridge comprising of HLB, Strata X-AW/CW, Isolute ENV+ (Biotage AB, Sweden) and ENVI-carb™ (Supelco, USA) sorbents, which are reversed phase, anion and cation exchange, polar and non-polar sorbents respectively.

Kilpinen et al. recently employed ML-SPE for the targeted analysis of 79 CECs in influent and effluent wastewater samples using both GC × GC-QToF-MS and LC-QToF-MS, allowing for the assessment of WWTP removal efficiencies. Within the same study, toxicological analysis using *Raphidocelis subcapitata* and *Daphnia magna* established that six of the CECs analysed were observed at concentrations above their predicted no-effect concentration [103]. Fig. 1 shows a GC × GC chromatogram from the analysis of a ML-SPE influent wastewater extract [40].

3.13. Solid phase micro extraction (SPME)

In SPME, the extraction phase is a non-volatile polymeric sorbent coated on a retractable silica fibre. Analytes are extracted through favourable partitioning coefficients between the polymer and the aqueous sample. After extraction, the fiber is desorbed in the GC inlet [104]. Several fiber types exist, with polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) being the most suitable for the extraction of non-polar compounds and the most commonly utilised [105].

Mixed phase SPME fibers, containing polar and non-polar functionality (PDMS/divinylbenzene), have been utilised with GC × GC. This method allowed for the detection of several more polar CECs in water samples (steroids, caffeine and methylparaben), without the need for derivatization [106]. Additionally, this fiber type was employed in the analysis of PPCPs, in Serbian water samples. Relic et al. (2017) used GC × GC paired with SPME for the targeted trace-level analysis of 14 musk compounds, allowing for their quantification in waste, river and drinking water samples [107].

3.14. Stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE)

In SBSE, analytes are extracted using a stir-bar coated with a sorbent, typically non-polar PDMS or a mixed mode PDMS/Ethylene glycol copolymer [108], immersed directly into the aqueous sample and stirred for a set period. The stir bar is then dried and desorbed via liquid desorption or thermal desorption [109]. A challenge in SBSE, especially for non-targeted analysis, is risk of bleeding during thermal desorption, complicating the identification of unknowns due to bleeding product presence (e.g., siloxanes) [110]. Gomez et al. (2011) employed SBSE with GC × GC-TOFMS to screen CECs in river and wastewater. Adding NaCl enhances SBSE's capability to extract more polar compounds by reducing their water solubility and increasing the PDMS/H₂O partition coefficient [70]. Adding 10 % MeOH along with NaCl reduces the sorption of more hydrophobic compounds on glass vial walls/liner, enhancing extraction efficiency. This method allowed for the quantification of targeted CECs with detection limits below 1 ng/L in full scan

mode and identification of various compounds in non-targeted analysis, including cholesterol, pharmaceuticals, illegal drugs, industrial chemicals, POPs and PCPs. Ochiai et al. (2011) also used salt addition to analyse more polar compounds, and carried out SBSE instead of LLE to extract organochlorine pesticides from river water samples using GC × GC-TOF-MS [58].

Murrell & Dorman compared SBSE to LLE for analysing CECs using GC × GC. They found SBSE discovered more CECs in wastewater due to its higher concentration factor, but noted its polarity bias with PDMS yielding inadequate recovery of more polar analytes [111]. In a subsequent study, they compared SBSE and LLE again for extracting CECs in wastewater. While both methods were similarly effective for target CECs in effluent samples, SBSE showed lower recovery for 24 out of 76 target analytes in influent samples due to stronger matrix effects [97]. The authors suggest using matrix matched or standard addition calibration for quantification to correct for matrix effects.

3.15. Derivatization methods

Derivatization in GC involves the conversion of an analyte into a different form before analysis, typically to enhance its volatility, stability, chromatographic properties, and the separation of more polar compounds [113]. Derivatization can be used in order to increase the number of detected polar compounds in non-targeted analysis, which is vital considering the toxicological relevance of polar components in wastewater, below are common derivatization strategies for the analysis of wastewater samples using GC, along with their advantages/disadvantages.

3.16. Silylation

Silylation replaces active hydrogens in compounds with a silyl group via nucleophilic substitution S_N2 reaction, commonly with amine, carboxylic acid and alcohol groups (see Fig. 2). This renders derivatives more volatile than the original compounds [17]. Widely used in the analysis of pharmaceuticals in wastewater [69,85,114,115], as well as more polar EDCs and hormones [73,74,116,117], improving their detection [118]. Furthermore, the injection of silylation reagent can derivatise silanol groups on the GC liner and column, reducing undesirable interactions with more polar analytes and thus lowering detection limits [119]. Unlike alkylation/acylation, where derivatives are extracted using a selective solvent, silylation is better suited for non-targeted analysis as injecting the sample with derivatization reagent allows for the characterization of both derivatised and underivatized analytes simultaneously. Commonly used silylation reagents are N,O-Bis

Fig. 1. GC × GC chromatogram of ML-SPE enriched influent wastewater extract. [40], with targeted CECs highlighted [103].

Fig. 2. Derivatization using N-methyl-N-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) (Villas-Bôas et al., 2011) [32].

(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (BSTFA) and N-methyl-N-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA), which may be used in conjunction with a catalyst, e.g. trimethyliodosilane (TMIS), to allow for the derivatization of ketones [120].

A limitation of silylation is that it requires completely anhydrous reaction conditions to proceed [32], which can be challenging during the evaporation to complete dryness and derivatization of wastewater extracts containing residual water.

3.17. Alkylation/acylation

Alkylation is a derivatization mechanism which involves the replacement of an acidic hydrogen by an alkyl group, generating the corresponding ether or ester as stable derivatives [17]. Unlike silylation, alkylation offers several benefits: less GC column and liner deterioration due to unconsumed derivatization agent, immediate derivatization without additional heating, and no need for anhydrous conditions [32]. Alkylation with methyl chloroformate (MCF) has been effectively used in the derivatization and detection of amino and non-amino organic acids via GC-MS [32]. Alkylation with acidic methanol has facilitated non-targeted analysis of polar wastewater extracts, allowing for the identification of phenols, benzene derivatives and organic acids [31], and acidic herbicides [31,121].

Acylation is used to target hydroxyl and basic NH groups. Acylation has the benefit of improving analyte stability by protecting unstable groups and by increasing the volatility and thermal stability of compounds with polar groups such as carbohydrates and amino acids. The use of halogenated acylation reagents improves the detectability when compared with electron capture detectors (ECD) [122]. However, acylation presents practical challenges, including the need to eliminate acidic by-products generated during derivatization and the reagents' incompatibility with moisture [17,122].

4. Data analysis

Data analysis is often cited as the bottleneck of GC × GC analytical workflows due to the large data files generated. While these files offer detailed fingerprinting, they can present challenges in interpretability [123]. Additionally, shifts in both 1st and 2nd dimension retention times must be compensated for in order to properly compare chromatograms [124]. The following sections detail both strategies for targeted analysis and common and emerging chemometric tools in non-targeted analysis.

4.1. Targeted analysis

Due to its ability to resolve interfering compounds in complex matrices, where co-eluting compounds in the 1st dimension can be resolved in the 2nd dimension, targeted analysis with GC × GC has shown to be quantitatively more accurate, sometimes leading to fewer overestimated concentrations compared to 1D-GC. Jover et al. (2009) demonstrated this phenomenon in the analysis of benzothiazoles, benzotriazoles and benzosulfonamides in wastewater, utilising both TIC and characteristic

ion/selective quantification methods [94].

4.2. Suspect screening

Over time, explorative analysis and new discoveries in non-targeted analysis should iteratively enhance our understanding of the composition of wastewater. Suspect screening lists may encompass compounds of interest that are known to occur in the matrix due to known composition or prior analysis. In addition, online resources such as the NORMAN network suspect list exchange contain suspect lists for compounds of environmental relevance [125].

Suspect screening may be carried out through cross referencing a suspect list with the output of non-targeted analysis [112]. However, this approach may yield false negatives in the case of co-eluting peaks, inadequate deconvolution and integration inconsistencies. Ideally, reference spectra, accurate mass selective ions and retention time windows should be utilised to identify and compare suspect compounds between samples. Harnett et al. (2023), demonstrate the use of an in-house machine learning assisted software to study contaminants in personal care products [126]. Target Analyte Find within Leco ChromaTOF (LECO Inc., USA) uses retention times in the 1st and 2nd dimension along with accurate masses corresponding to molecular formulae, to determine the presence and EIC response for suspects. Within GC-Image (GC Image LLC, Nebraska, USA), Computer Language for Identifying Chemicals (CLIC) expressions may be created for suspect screening.

4.3. Non-targeted analysis methods

Non-targeted methods in GC × GC may be grouped into the following three categories, peak table, pixel based and tile based approaches [127]. Recent reviews by Trinklein et al. (2023) [127], Stefanuto et al. (2021) [128] and Freye et al. (2020), describe and compare these approaches in detail, therefore for the purposes of this review, these approaches will be briefly summarised below, in the context of non-targeted analysis of CECS.

4.4. Peak/Blob comparison approaches

The common method for comparing GC × GC chromatograms involves the processing of chromatograms within the chromatography software (phase shifting, baseline correction, integration and MS searching), then exporting, filtering, and comparing peak tables. GC-Image (GC Image LLC, Nebraska, USA) is the most popular chromatography data system for GC × GC data. Investigator/MDC Investigator™ is a non-targeted analysis tool in GC-Image. Chromatograms are processed and aligned using a transformation algorithm, compensating for retention time shifting via landmark alignment with reliably identified compounds. A feature template divides the chromatogram into discrete areas containing individual analytes, which is then applied to the aligned chromatograms. The volume within each area is then compared between samples. Tools are available to perform principal component analysis, Fisher ratios and F-tests. A major limitation of this approach is that comparison of the total TIC volume within each region assumes that peaks are completely resolved and no co-elution occurs within the defined areas [129]. Therefore, there is a high risk of false positives using this approach, especially when it is applied to a complex sample matrix containing compounds of diverse chemical classes, such as wastewater.

4.5. Pixel-based approaches

The two-dimensional, imagelike structure of GC × GC chromatograms allows for the application of image processing tools for their analysis, including pixel-based analysis [124]. Pixel-based approaches typically carry out the phase shifting, baseline subtraction, alignment to

correct for retention time drift in both dimensions, normalisation, and scaling of all chromatograms of interest, prior to comparison. Principal component analysis (PCA) can then be carried out, yielding 2D loading plots which can be easily inspected due to their equivalence to a GC \times GC chromatogram. Via inspection of the loadings, the major sources of variation within the samples can be investigated, reducing dimensionality and serving as a starting point for further investigation. A detailed walkthrough of pixel-based analysis of GC \times GC chromatograms has been described by Furbo et al. (2014) [130]. This approach has been used for the non-targeted analysis of CECs in freshwater sediments using GC \times GC, allowing several sources of contaminants to be identified [131]. A challenge in pixel-based analysis can be in chromatographic alignment, as uncorrected shifts in both the 1st and 2nd dimension may result in the modelling of shifts instead of chemical information [127]. Multiple alignment algorithms have been developed to remedy this issue, such as 2D correlation optimized warping [132] and interval correlation optimized shifting [133].

4.6. Tile-based approaches

Tile-based analysis was developed to compensate for the aforementioned alignment issues and is available as commercial software in Chromcompare+ (SepSolve Analytical Ltd, UK) and ChromaTOF® Tile (LECO, St. Joseph, MI, USA). As in the previous approaches chromatograms are imported, processed and aligned. Subsequently, a two-dimensional grid covers the entire chromatogram, comprised of two-dimensional tiles, with each tile sufficiently large enough to capture the retention time variation of components in both the 1st and 2nd dimension and sums all signals within the tile as a function of each mass channel (m/z) [134]. Due to the great number of features created with this method, tile-based analysis typically relies on supervised means to reduce dimensionality, where sample class is specified for each sample. Typically the F-Ratio is calculated (class-to-class variation of the signal divided by the sum of the within-class variations of the signal) for each tile, as a supervised means of reducing dimensionality and prioritising compounds of interest within the sample set [135]. As each tile represents a single m/z , redundancy will occur as multiple tiles will correspond to the ions in each unique compound's spectra. A "pinning and clustering" algorithm can then be carried out to remove redundant hits, by refocusing tiles to the peak apex and clustering tiles with matching retention times onto the original pixel level data [127,136].

4.7. Annotation of non-target features in GC \times GC-MS

Common to each non-target methodology is an output list of non-target features. Confident identification and annotation of these features in a standardised fashion is essential in communicating and publishing the results of non-targeted analysis. Schymanski et al. [28] created an identification confidence framework in 2014, which has been widely adopted in the field of environmental analytical chemistry, using both GC and LC. Optimized for LC-HRMS/MS, the framework relies on MS and MS² spectra, MS isotope and adduct ions and retention times. Addressing the Schymanski method's limitations in GC, Koelmel et al. (2022) developed a five level identification confidence framework using common metrics in the GC field, including blank filtering, (reverse) spectral matches, high-resolution mass filters or exact mass spectral matches, RI, and molecular ion [29]. While an improvement on previous frameworks, retention time/retention indices in the second dimension allows for an additional level of confidence in annotation in GC \times GC, however this is not yet captured within any current identification confidence framework.

5. Conclusion and perspectives

Recent years have highlighted the analytical challenges posed by complex environmental samples like wastewater, which contain diverse

chemical sources and classes, often with compounds of interest present at trace concentrations. GC \times GC has emerged as a powerful tool in the characterisation of such samples, providing deeper insight into the contaminant composition. It identifies new contaminants obscured by co-elution in conventional GC-MS, more accurately quantifying target analytes by improving resolution from matrix interferences, and detects trace contaminants more effectively through modulation-based sensitivity enhancement. Due to its inherent complexity, GC \times GC might appear intimidating in the analytical laboratory. Hence, this review offers a comprehensive summary to guide analysts new to the field in navigating toward meaningful discoveries. Strategies for sample preparation and derivatization have been outlined, to enrich and detect the greatest amount of the more polar CECs in wastewater. Considerations for column and detector choice have been summarised in the context of specific targeted groups of CECs. Finally, the most common strategies for targeted, suspect and non-target screening have been outlined, with the advantages and limitations of each approach highlighted.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jason Devers: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **David I. Pattison:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Asger B. Hansen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jan H. Christensen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

6. Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Jason Devers reports financial support was provided by Innovation Fund Denmark. Jason Devers reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Jan H Christensen reports financial support was provided by Innovation Fund Denmark. Jan H Christensen reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

This review was prepared in the context of research carried out for the VANDALF project under grant agreement no 9067-00032B and supported by the Innovation Fund Denmark, in addition to the D4RunOff project, funded by the the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme with Grant Agreement number 101060638.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2024.127032>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] Y. Luo, W. Guo, H.H. Ngo, L.D. Nghiem, F.I. Hai, J. Zhang, S. Liang, X.C. Wang, A review on the occurrence of micropollutants in the aquatic environment and their fate and removal during wastewater treatment, *Science of the Total*

- Environment 473–474 (2014) 619–641, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.12.065>.
- [2] P.A. Neale, R. Altenburger, S. Ait-Aïssa, F. Brion, W. Busch, G. de Aragão Umbuzeiro, M.S. Denison, D. Du Pasquier, K. Hilscherová, H. Hollert, D. A. Morales, J. Novák, R. Schlichting, T.B. Seiler, H. Serra, Y. Shao, A.J. Tindall, K. E. Tollefsen, T.D. Williams, B.I. Escher, Development of a bioanalytical test battery for water quality monitoring: fingerprinting identified micropollutants and their contribution to effects in surface water, *Water Res.* 123 (2017) 734–750, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.07.016>.
 - [3] B.I. Escher, C. Van Daele, M. Dutt, J.Y.M. Tang, R. Altenburger, Most oxidative stress response in water samples comes from unknown chemicals: the need for effect-based water quality trigger values, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47 (2013) 7002–7011, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es304793h>.
 - [4] J.Y.M. Tang, S. McCarty, E. Glenn, P.A. Neale, M.S.J. Warne, B.I. Escher, Mixture effects of organic micropollutants present in water: towards the development of effect-based water quality trigger values for baseline toxicity, *Water Res.* 47 (2013) 3300–3314, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2013.03.011>.
 - [5] V. Dulio, B. van Bavel, E. Brorström-Lundén, J. Harmsen, J. Hollender, M. Schlabach, J. Slobodnik, K. Thomas, J. Koschorreck, Emerging pollutants in the EU: 10 years of NORMAN in support of environmental policies and regulations, *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 30 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-018-0135-3>.
 - [6] D. Barceló, M. Petrović, *Emerging Contaminants from industrial and municipal waste: occurrence. Analysis and Effects*, 2008.
 - [7] T. Deblonde, C. Cossu-Leguille, P. Hartemann, Emerging pollutants in wastewater: a review of the literature, *Int. J. Hyg Environ. Health* 214 (2011) 442–448, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2011.08.002>.
 - [8] K. Kümmerer, Emerging contaminants versus micro-pollutants, *Clean* 39 (2011) 889–890, <https://doi.org/10.1002/clean.201110002>.
 - [9] N.H. Tran, M. Reinhard, K.Y.H. Gin, Occurrence and fate of emerging contaminants in municipal wastewater treatment plants from different geographical regions—a review, *Water Res.* 133 (2018) 182–207, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.12.029>.
 - [10] K. Nödler, O. Hillebrand, K. Idzik, M. Strathmann, F. Schipferski, J. Zirlawagen, T. Licha, Occurrence and fate of the angiotensin II receptor antagonist transformation product valsartan acid in the water cycle - a comparative study with selected β -blockers and the persistent anthropogenic wastewater indicators carbamazepine and aceculfame, *Water Res.* 47 (2013) 6650–6659, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2013.08.034>.
 - [11] Y. Peng, S. Hall, L. Gautam, Drugs of abuse in drinking water – a review of current detection methods, occurrence, elimination and health risks, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* 85 (2016) 232–240, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2016.09.011>.
 - [12] J. Margot, L. Rossi, D.A. Barry, C. Holliger, A review of the fate of micropollutants in wastewater treatment plants, *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water* 2 (2015) 457–487, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1090>.
 - [13] J.Q. Jiang, Z. Zhou, V.K. Sharma, Occurrence, transportation, monitoring and treatment of emerging micro-pollutants in waste water - a review from global views, *Microchem. J.* 110 (2013) 292–300, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2013.04.014>.
 - [14] H. Rüdell, W. Körner, T. Letzel, M. Neumann, K. Nödler, T. Reemtsma, Persistent, mobile and toxic substances in the environment: a spotlight on current research and regulatory activities, *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 32 (2020) 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-019-0286-x>.
 - [15] *Joint Norman, Water Europe Position Paper, Contaminants of Emerging Concern in Urban Wastewater Joint NORMAN and Water Europe Position Paper*, 2019, pp. 1–21.
 - [16] P. Rostkowski, P. Haglund, C. Dye, M. Schlabach, Non-target Screening of Environmental Samples by Low and High Resolution Time of Flight mass, Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Environmental Science and Technology, Athens, Greece, 2013, pp. 5–7, <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.5075.4880>, 5-7 Septembre 2013.
 - [17] T. Reemtsma, J.B. Quintana, *Organic Pollutants in the Water Cycle*, first ed., Wiley, 2006.
 - [18] J.L. Malvar, J.L. Santos, J. Martín, I. Aparicio, E. Alonso, Routine analytical method for monitoring the main metabolites for a recurrent group of parabens and pharmaceuticals in wastewater and tap water, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 411 (2019) 6625–6635, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-019-02035-2>.
 - [19] S. Tisler, N. Engler, M.B. Jørgensen, K. Kilpinen, G. Tomasi, J.H. Christensen, From data to reliable conclusions: identification and comparison of persistent micropollutants and transformation products in 37 wastewater samples by non-target screening prioritization, *Water Res.* 219 (2022) 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.118599>.
 - [20] J. Mechelke, P. Longrée, H. Singer, J. Hollender, Vacuum-assisted evaporative concentration combined with LC-HRMS/MS for ultra-trace-level screening of organic micropollutants in environmental water samples, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* (2019) 2555–2567, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-019-01696-3>.
 - [21] T. Smital, S. Terzic, R. Zaja, I. Senta, B. Pivčević, M. Popović, I. Mikac, K. E. Tollefsen, K.V. Thomas, M. Ahel, Assessment of toxicological profiles of the municipal wastewater effluents using chemical analyses and bioassays, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 74 (2011) 844–851, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2010.11.010>.
 - [22] M. Caban, N. Migowska, P. Stepnowski, M. Kwiatkowski, J. Kumirska, Matrix effects and recovery calculations in analyses of pharmaceuticals based on the determination of β -blockers and β -agonists in environmental samples, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1258 (2012) 117–127, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2012.08.029>.
 - [23] A. Samokhin, K. Sotnezova, V. Lashin, I. Revelsky, Evaluation of mass spectral library search algorithms implemented in commercial software, *J. Mass Spectrom.* 50 (2015) 820–825, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jms.3591>.
 - [24] W.&S. Ltd, *Wiley Registry of Mass Spectral Data* 2023, 2023.
 - [25] *National Institute of Standards and Technology, NIST 23 Mass Spectral Library*, 2023.
 - [26] D.A. Vargas Medina, E.V.S. Maciel, N.G. Pereira dos Santos, F.M. Lancas, The overshadowed role of electron ionization–mass spectrometry in analytical biotechnology, *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 82 (2023) 102965, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2023.102965>.
 - [27] V.I. Babushok, Chromatographic retention indices in identification of chemical compounds, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* 69 (2015) 98–104, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2015.04.001>.
 - [28] E.L. Schymanski, J. Jeon, R. Gulde, K. Fenner, M. Ruff, H.P. Singer, J. Hollender, Identifying small molecules via high resolution mass spectrometry: communicating confidence, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48 (2014) 2097–2098, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es5002105>.
 - [29] J.P. Koelmel, H. Xie, E.J. Price, E.Z. Lin, K.E. Manz, P. Stelben, M.K. Paige, S. Papazian, J. Okeme, D.P. Jones, D. Barupal, J.A. Bowden, P. Rostkowski, K. D. Pennell, V. Nikiforov, T. Wang, X. Hu, Y. Lai, G.W. Miller, D.I. Walker, J. W. Martin, K.J. Godri Pollitt, An actionable annotation scoring framework for gas chromatography-high-resolution mass spectrometry, *Exposome* 2 (2022) 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1093/exposome/osac007>.
 - [30] T. Reemtsma, U. Berger, H.P.H. Arp, H. Gallard, T.P. Knepper, M. Neumann, J. B. Quintana, P. De Voogt, Mind the gap: persistent and mobile organic compounds - water contaminants that slip through, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50 (2016) 10308–10315, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b03338>.
 - [31] J. Hrubik, B. Glisic, A. Tubic, I. Ivancev-Tumbas, R. Kovacevic, D. Samardzija, N. Andric, S. Kaisarevic, Toxicological and chemical investigation of untreated municipal wastewater: fraction- and species-specific toxicity, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 127 (2016) 153–162, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2016.01.018>.
 - [32] S.G. Villas-Bôas, K.F. Smart, S. Sivakumaran, G.A. Lane, Alkylation or silylation for analysis of amino and non-amino organic acids by GC-MS? *Metabolites* 1 (2011) 3–20, <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo1010003>.
 - [33] Z. Liu, J.B. Phillips, Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography using an on-column thermal modulator interface, *J. Chromatogr. Sci.* 29 (1991) 227–231, <https://doi.org/10.1093/chromsci/29.6.227>.
 - [34] L. Mondello, *COMPREHENSIVE CHROMATOGRAPHY IN COMBINATION WITH MASS SPECTROMETRY*, Wiley, 2011.
 - [35] A. Mostafa, M. Edwards, T. Görecki, Optimization aspects of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1255 (2012) 38–55, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2012.02.064>.
 - [36] J. Mommers, S. van der Wal, Column selection and optimization for comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography: a review, *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.* 51 (2021) 183–202, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408347.2019.1707643>.
 - [37] E.M.M. Wanda, H. Nyoni, B.B. Mamba, T.A.M. Msagati, Occurrence of emerging micropollutants in water systems in Gauteng, Mpumalanga, and North West provinces, South Africa, *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 14 (2017) 8–20, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14010079>.
 - [38] O. Pani, T. Görecki, Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography (GC×GC) in environmental analysis and monitoring, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 386 (2006) 1013–1023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-006-0568-1>.
 - [39] V. Matamoros, E. Jover, J.M. Bayona, Part-per-Trillion determination of pharmaceuticals, pesticides, and related organic contaminants in river water by solid-phase extraction followed by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 82 (2010) 699–706, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac902340e>.
 - [40] J. Devers, D.I. Pattison, J.H. Christensen, Second dimension retention indices in “normal” orthogonality comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography using single standard injection generated isovolatility curves, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1683 (2022) 463548, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2022.463548>.
 - [41] M. Jiang, Facile approach for calculation of second dimensional retention indices in comprehensive two dimensional gas chromatography with single injection, *Anal. Chem.* 91 (2019) 4085–4091, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.8b05717>.
 - [42] M. Jiang, C. Kulsing, Y. Nolvachai, P.J. Marriott, Two-dimensional retention indices improve component identification in comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography of saffron, *Anal. Chem.* 87 (2015) 5753–5761, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.5b00953>.
 - [43] M.S.S. Amaral, Y. Nolvachai, P.J. Marriott, Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography advances in technology and applications: biennial update, *Anal. Chem.* 92 (2020) 85–104, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b05412>.
 - [44] S. Schöneich, T.J. Trinklein, C.G. Warren, R.E. Synovec, A systematic investigation of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography time-of-flight mass spectrometry with dynamic pressure gradient modulation for high peak capacity separations, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1134 (2020) 115–124, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2020.08.023>.
 - [45] H.D. Bahaghighat, C.E. Freye, R.E. Synovec, Recent advances in modulator technology for comprehensive two dimensional gas chromatography, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* 113 (2019) 379–391, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2018.04.016>.
 - [46] J.V. Seeley, Theoretical study of incomplete sampling of the first dimension in comprehensive two-dimensional chromatography, *J. Chromatogr. A* 962 (2002) 21–27, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673\(02\)0461-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(02)0461-2).

- [47] SepSolve Analytical, INSIGHT® Outstanding GC×GC performance for both flow and thermal modulation, Sepsolve Analytical (2023) 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bdj.2010.869>.
- [48] J. Luong, X. Guan, S. Xu, R. Gras, R.A. Shellie, Thermal independent modulator for comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography, *Anal. Chem.* 88 (2016) 8428–8432, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.6b02525>.
- [49] ZOEX Corporation, ZX2 Thermal Modulator 2828 (2023) 1–2.
- [50] H. Boswell, K.T. Carrillo, T. Górecki, Evaluation of the performance of cryogenic thermal modulation-based comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography-time-of-flight mass spectrometry (GC×GC-TOFMS) for the qualitative analysis of a complex bitumen sample, *Separations* 7 (2020) 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations7010013>.
- [51] M.R. Jacobs, M. Edwards, T. Górecki, P.N. Nesterenko, R.A. Shellie, Evaluation of a miniaturised single-stage thermal modulator for comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography of petroleum contaminated soils, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1463 (2016) 162–168, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2016.08.009>.
- [52] S. Wohlfahrt, M. Fischer, J. Varga, M.R. Saraji-Bozorgzad, G. Matuschek, T. Denner, R. Zimmermann, Dual-stage consumable-free thermal modulator for the hyphenation of thermal analysis, gas chromatography, and mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 88 (2016) 640–644, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.5b04183>.
- [53] A.M. Muscalu, M. Edwards, T. Górecki, E.J. Reiner, Evaluation of a single-stage consumable-free modulator for comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography: analysis of polychlorinated biphenyls, organochlorine pesticides and chlorobenzenes, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1391 (2015) 93–101, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2015.02.074>.
- [54] S. Schöneich, D.V. Gough, T.J. Trinklein, R.E. Synovec, Dynamic pressure gradient modulation for comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography with time-of-flight mass spectrometry detection, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1620 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2020.460982>.
- [55] C.J. Venkatramani, J. Xu, J.B. Phillips, Separation orthogonality in temperature-programmed comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography, *Anal. Chem.* 68 (1996) 1486–1492, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac951048b>.
- [56] P.H. Stefanuto, J.F. Focant, Columns and column configurations, in: *Separation Science and Technology*, Elsevier Inc., New York, 2020, pp. 69–88, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813745-1.00003-9>.
- [57] C.F. Poole, S.K. Poole, Ionic liquid stationary phases for gas chromatography, *J. Separ. Sci.* 34 (2011) 888–900, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201000724>.
- [58] N. Ochiai, T. Ieda, K. Sasamoto, Y. Takazawa, S. Hashimoto, A. Fushimi, K. Tanabe, Stir bar sorptive extraction and comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography coupled to high-resolution time-of-flight mass spectrometry for ultra-trace analysis of organochlorine pesticides in river water, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1218 (2011) 6851–6860, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2011.08.027>.
- [59] N.V. Hung, C. Mohabeer, M. Vaccaro, S. Marcotte, V. Agasse-Peulon, L. Abdelouahed, B. Taouk, P. Cardinael, Development of two-dimensional gas chromatography (GC×GC) coupled with Orbitrap-technology-based mass spectrometry: interest in the identification of biofuel composition, *J. Mass Spectrom.* 55 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1002/jms.4495>.
- [60] O. Vaye, R.S. Ngumbu, D. Xia, A review of the application of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography MS-based techniques for the analysis of persistent organic pollutants and ultra-trace level of organic pollutants in environmental samples, *Rev. Anal. Chem.* 41 (2022) 63–73, <https://doi.org/10.1515/revac-2022-0034>.
- [61] Shimadzu Corporation, Shimadzu Analytical and Measuring Instruments 24 (2024) C054–E032.
- [62] V. de Hoffmann, Edmond; Stroobant, *Mass Spectrometry: Principles and Applications*, third ed., Wiley, 2007.
- [63] J.L. Johnson, N.G. Dodder, N. Mladenov, L. Steinberg, W.H. Richardot, E. Hoh, Comparison of trace organic chemical removal efficiencies between aerobic and anaerobic membrane bioreactors treating municipal wastewater, *ACS ES and T Water* 4 (2024) 1381–1392, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsestwater.3c00542>.
- [64] S. Fernando, A. Renaguli, M.S. Milligan, J.J. Pagano, P.K. Hopke, T.M. Holten, B.S. Crimmins, Comprehensive analysis of the great lakes top predator fish for novel halogenated organic contaminants by GC×GC-HR-ToF mass spectrometry, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 52 (2018) 2909–2917, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b05999>.
- [65] S.A. Ortiz de García, G. Pinto Pinto, P.A. García-Encina, R. Irusta-Mata, Ecotoxicity and environmental risk assessment of pharmaceuticals and personal care products in aquatic environments and wastewater treatment plants, *Ecotoxicology* 23 (2014) 1517–1533, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10646-014-1293-8>.
- [66] O. Frédéric, P. Yves, Pharmaceuticals in hospital wastewater: their ecotoxicity and contribution to the environmental hazard of the effluent, *Chemosphere* 115 (2014) 31–39, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.01.016>.
- [67] S. Comber, M. Gardner, P. Sörme, D. Leverett, B. Ellor, Active pharmaceutical ingredients entering the aquatic environment from wastewater treatment works: a cause for concern? *Science of the Total Environment* 613–614 (2018) 538–547, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.09.101>.
- [68] M.S. Beldean-Galea, V. Coman, F. Copaciu, D. Thiébaud, J. Vial, Simultaneous identification of Fenton degradation by-products of diclofenac, ibuprofen and ketoprofen in aquatic media by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry, *Rev. Roum. Chem.* 59 (2014) 1021–1027.
- [69] P. Lacina, L. Mravcová, M. Vávrová, Application of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography with mass spectrometric detection for the analysis of selected drug residues in wastewater and surface water, *J. Environ. Sci. (China)* 25 (2013) 204–212, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-0742\(12\)60006-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-0742(12)60006-0).
- [70] M.J. Gómez, S. Herrera, D. Solé, E. García-Calvo, A.R. Fernández-Alba, Automatic searching and evaluation of priority and emerging contaminants in wastewater and river water by stir bar sorptive extraction followed by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography-time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 83 (2011) 2638–2647, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac102909g>.
- [71] L. Castillo Meza, P. Piotrowski, J. Farnan, T.L. Tasker, B. Xiong, B. Weggler, K. Murrell, F.L. Dorman, J.P. Vanden Heuvel, W.D. Burgos, Detection and removal of biologically active organic micropollutants from hospital wastewater, *Sci. Total Environ.* 700 (2020) 134469, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134469>.
- [72] Z.L. Zhang, A. Hibberd, J.L. Zhou, Optimisation of derivatisation for the analysis of estrogenic compounds in water by solid-phase extraction gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 577 (2006) 52–61, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2006.06.029>.
- [73] A. Azzouz, E. Ballesteros, Trace analysis of endocrine disrupting compounds in environmental water samples by use of solid-phase extraction and gas chromatography with mass spectrometry detection, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1360 (2014) 248–257, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2014.07.059>.
- [74] S.R. Gunatilake, T.L. Clark, J.M. Rodriguez, T.E. Mlsna, Determination of five estrogens in wastewater using a comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatograph, *Anal. Methods* 6 (2014) 5652–5658, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ay00960f>.
- [75] T. Ieda, Y. Horii, G. Petrick, N. Yamashita, N. Ochiai, K. Kannan, Analysis of nonylphenol isomers in a technical mixture and in water by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 39 (2005) 7202–7207, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es050568d>.
- [76] S. Schulze, D. Zahn, R. Montes, R. Rodil, J.B. Quintana, T.P. Knepper, T. Reemtsma, U. Berger, Occurrence of emerging persistent and mobile organic contaminants in European water samples, *Water Res.* 153 (2019) 80–90, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.01.008>.
- [77] M. Harju, C. Danielsson, P. Haglund, Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography of the 209 polychlorinated biphenyls, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1019 (2003) 111–126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2003.08.100>.
- [78] P. Dimitriou-Christidis, A. Bonvin, S. Samanipour, J. Hollender, R. Rutler, J. Westphale, J. Gros, J.S. Arey, GC×GC quantification of priority and emerging nonpolar halogenated micropollutants in all types of wastewater matrices: analysis methodology, chemical occurrence, and partitioning, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49 (2015) 7914–7925, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es5049122>.
- [79] R.C. Buck, J. Franklin, U. Berger, J.M. Conder, I.T. Cousins, P. De Voogt, A. A. Jensen, K. Kannan, S.A. Mabury, S.P.J. van Leeuwen, Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances in the environment: terminology, classification, and origins, *Integrated Environ. Assess. Manag.* 7 (2011) 513–541, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.258>.
- [80] I.K. Dimzon, J. Westerveld, C. Gremmel, T. Frömel, T.P. Knepper, P. de Voogt, Sampling and simultaneous determination of volatile per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in wastewater treatment plant air and water, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 409 (2017) 1395–1404, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-016-0072-1>.
- [81] J.S. Casey, S.R. Jackson, J. Ryan, S.R. Newton, The use of gas chromatography – high resolution mass spectrometry for suspect screening and non-targeted analysis of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1693 (2023) 463884, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2023.463884>.
- [82] H.P.H. Arp, S.E. Hale, REACH: improvement of guidance and methods for the identification and assessment of PMT/vPvM substances, *The National Audit of Violence* (2003 - 2005) 126 (2019) 1–131.
- [83] P.H. Howard, D.C.G. Muir, Identifying new persistent and bioaccumulative organics among chemicals in commerce. III: byproducts, impurities, and transformation products, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47 (2013) 5259–5266, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es4004075>.
- [84] K.M. Blum, P.L. Andersson, G. Renman, L. Ahrens, M. Gros, K. Wiberg, P. Haglund, Non-target screening and prioritization of potentially persistent, bioaccumulating and toxic domestic wastewater contaminants and their removal in on-site and large-scale sewage treatment plants, *Sci. Total Environ.* 575 (2017) 265–275, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.09.135>.
- [85] Á. Sebok, A. Vasánits-Zsigrai, G. Palkó, G. Zárny, I. Molnár-Perl, Identification and quantification of ibuprofen, naproxen, ketoprofen and diclofenac present in waste-waters, as their trimethylsilyl derivatives, by gas chromatography mass spectrometry, *Talanta* 76 (2008) 642–650, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2008.04.008>.
- [86] G. Semard, A. Bruchet, P. Cardinael, J.P. Bouillon, Use of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography for the broad screening of hazardous contaminants in urban wastewaters, *Water Sci. Technol.* 57 (2008) 1983–1989, <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2008.615>.
- [87] N. Ramírez, F. Borrull, R.M. Marcé, Simultaneous determination of parabens and synthetic musks in water by stir-bar sorptive extraction and thermal desorption-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, *J. Separ. Sci.* 35 (2012) 580–588, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201100887>.
- [88] K.M. Blum, C. Gallampos, P.L. Andersson, G. Renman, A. Renman, P. Haglund, Comprehensive assessment of organic contaminant removal from on-site sewage treatment facility effluent by char-fortified filter beds, *J. Hazard Mater.* 361 (2019) 111–122, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.08.009>.
- [89] L. Castillo Meza, P. Piotrowski, J. Farnan, T.L. Tasker, B. Xiong, B. Weggler, K. Murrell, F.L. Dorman, J.P. Vanden Heuvel, W.D. Burgos, Detection and removal of biologically active organic micropollutants from hospital wastewater,

- Sci. Total Environ. 700 (2020) 134469, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134469>.
- [90] N. Mladenov, N.G. Dodder, L. Steinberg, W. Richardot, J. Johnson, B. S. Martincigh, C. Buckley, T. Lawrence, E. Hoh, Persistence and removal of trace organic compounds in centralized and decentralized wastewater treatment systems, *Chemosphere* 286 (2022) 131621, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.131621>.
- [91] R.P. Eganhouse, J. Pontolillo, R.B. Gaines, G.S. Frynsinger, F.L.P. Gabriel, H.P. E. Kohler, W. Giger, L.B. Barber, Isomer-specific determination of 4-nonylphenols using comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography/time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 43 (2009) 9306–9313, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es902622z>.
- [92] C. Zhang, R.P. Eganhouse, J. Pontolillo, I.M. Cozzarelli, Y. Wang, Determination of nonylphenol isomers in landfill leachate and municipal wastewater using steam distillation extraction coupled with comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography/time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1230 (2012) 110–116, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2011.12.109>.
- [93] M. Kopperi, J. Parshintsev, J. Ruiz-Jiménez, M.L. Riekkola, Nontargeted evaluation of the fate of steroids during wastewater treatment by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography–time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Control Ser.* 23 (2016) 17008–17017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-016-6800-4>.
- [94] E. Jover, V. Matamoros, J.M. Bayona, Characterization of benzothiazoles, benzotriazoles and benzosulfonamides in aqueous matrices by solid-phase extraction followed by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography coupled to time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1216 (2009) 4013–4019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2009.02.052>.
- [95] S. Prebihalo, A. Brockman, J. Cochran, F.L. Dorman, Determination of emerging contaminants in wastewater utilizing comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography coupled with time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1419 (2015) 109–115, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2015.09.080>.
- [96] K.M. Blum, P.L. Andersson, L. Ahrens, K. Wiberg, P. Haglund, Persistence, mobility and bioavailability of emerging organic contaminants discharged from sewage treatment plants, *Sci. Total Environ.* 612 (2018) 1532–1542, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.09.006>.
- [97] K.A. Murrell, F.L. Dorman, A comparison of liquid-liquid extraction and stir bar sorptive extraction for multiclass organic contaminants in wastewater by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography time of flight mass spectrometry, *Talanta* 221 (2021) 121481, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2020.121481>.
- [98] K.A. Murrell, F.L. Dorman, Characterization and quantification of methylbenzotriazoles and chloromethyl-benzotriazoles produced from disinfection processes in wastewater treatment, *Sci. Total Environ.* 699 (2020) 134310, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134310>.
- [99] S. Hashimoto, H. Matsukami, T. Ieda, G. Suzuki, Comprehensive screening of polybromochlorodibenzop-dioxins, dibenzofurans as mixed halogenated compounds in wastewater samples from industrial facilities by GC×GC/ToFMS and post-data processing, *Chemosphere* 276 (2021) 130085, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130085>.
- [100] K.P. Ishida, R.F. Luna, W.H. Richardot, N. Lopez-Galvez, M.H. Plumlee, N. G. Dodder, E. Hoh, Nontargeted analysis of trace organic constituents in reverse osmosis and UV-aop product waters of a potable reuse facility, *ACS ES&T Water* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsestwater.1c00265>.
- [101] X.Y. Zhang, Y. Lu, Y. Du, W.L. Wang, L.L. Yang, Q.Y. Wu, Comprehensive GC×GC-qMS with a mass-to-charge ratio difference extraction method to identify new brominated byproducts during ozonation and their toxicity assessment, *J. Hazard Mater.* 403 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.124103>.
- [102] J. Pawliszyn, H.L. Lord, *Handbook of Sample Preparation*, Wiley, 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780813823621>.
- [103] K. Kilpinen, J. Devers, M. Castro, S. Tisler, M.B. Jørgensen, P. Mortensen, J. H. Christensen, Catchment area, fate, and environmental risks investigation of micropollutants in Danish wastewater, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Control Ser.* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-30331-z>.
- [104] H. Grefslie Ugland, M. Krogh, K.E. Rasmussen, Automated determination of “Ecstasy” and amphetamines in urine by SPME and capillary gas chromatography after propylchloroformate derivatization, *J. Pharmaceut. Biomed. Anal.* 19 (1999) 463–475, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085\(98\)00240-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085(98)00240-4).
- [105] M. Llompart, M. Lourido, P. Landín, C. García-Jares, R. Cela, Optimization of a derivatization—solid-phase microextraction method for the analysis of thirty phenolic pollutants in water samples, *J. Chromatogr. A* 963 (2002) 137–148, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673\(02\)00646-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(02)00646-5).
- [106] P.C.F. Lima Gomes, B.B. Barnes, Á.J. Santos-Neto, F.M. Lencas, N.H. Snow, Determination of steroids, caffeine and methylparaben in water using solid phase microextraction-comprehensive two dimensional gas chromatography-time of flight mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1299 (2013) 126–130, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2013.05.023>.
- [107] D. Relić, A. Popović, Đ. Đorđević, J. Časlavský, Occurrence of synthetic musk compounds in surface, underground, waste and processed water samples in Belgrade, Serbia, *Environ. Earth Sci.* 76 (2017) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-017-6441-z>.
- [108] N. Ochiai, K. Sasamoto, F. David, P. Sandra, Recent developments of stir bar sorptive extraction for food applications: extension to polar solutes, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 66 (2018) 7249–7255, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.8b02182>.
- [109] A.M. Casas Ferreira, M. Möder, M.E. Fernández Laespada, GC-MS determination of parabens, triclosan and methyl triclosan in water by in situ derivatization and stir-bar sorptive extraction, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 399 (2011) 945–953, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-010-4339-7>.
- [110] M. Guardia, S. Armenta, *Green Analytical Chemistry*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2010.
- [111] K.A. Murrell, F.L. Dorman, A suspect screening analysis for contaminants of emerging concern in municipal wastewater and surface water using liquid-liquid extraction and stir bar sorptive extraction, *Anal. Methods* 12 (2020) 4487–4495, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0ay01179g>.
- [112] K.A. Murrell, F.L. Dorman, A suspect screening analysis for contaminants of emerging concern in municipal wastewater and surface water using liquid-liquid extraction and stir bar sorptive extraction, *Anal. Methods* 12 (2020) 4487–4495, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0ay01179g>.
- [113] D.L. Lin, S.M. Wang, C.H. Wu, B.G. Chen, R.H. Liu, Chemical derivatization for the analysis of drugs by GC-MS - a conceptual review, *J. Food Drug Anal.* 16 (2008) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.38212/2224-6614.2373>.
- [114] A. Togola, H. Budzinski, Multi-residue analysis of pharmaceutical compounds in aqueous samples, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1177 (2008) 150–158, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2007.10.105>.
- [115] K.J. Bisceglia, J.T. Yu, M. Coelhan, E.J. Bouwer, A.L. Roberts, Trace determination of pharmaceuticals and other wastewater-derived micropollutants by solid phase extraction and gas chromatography/mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1217 (2010) 558–564, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2009.11.062>.
- [116] T. Zhang, X. Chen, P. Liang, C. Liu, Determination of phenolic compounds in wastewater by liquid-phase microextraction coupled with gas chromatography, *Journal of Chromatographic Science* 44 (2006) 619–624, <https://doi.org/10.1093/chromsci/44.10.619>.
- [117] M. Möder, P. Braun, F. Lange, S. Schrader, W. Lorenz, Determination of endocrine disrupting compounds and acidic drugs in water by coupling of derivatization, gas chromatography and negative-chemical ionization mass spectrometry, *Clean* 35 (2007) 444–451, <https://doi.org/10.1002/clen.200720001>.
- [118] J.A. Bowden, D.M. Colosi, D.C. Mora-Montero, T.J. Garrett, R.A. Yost, Evaluation of derivatization strategies for the comprehensive analysis of endocrine disrupting compounds using GC/MS, *Journal of Chromatographic Science* 47 (2009) 44–51, <https://doi.org/10.1093/chromsci/47.1.44>.
- [119] M. Ljoncheva, E. Heath, D. Heath, S. Džeroski, T. Kosjek, Contaminants of emerging concern: silylation procedures, evaluation of the stability of silyl derivatives and associated measurement uncertainty, *Sci. Total Environ.* 899 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165669>.
- [120] K. Fang, X. Pan, B. Huang, J. Liu, Y. Wang, J. Gao, Simultaneous derivatization of hydroxyl and ketone groups for the analysis of steroid hormones by GC-MS, *Chromatographia* 72 (2010) 949–956, <https://doi.org/10.1365/s10337-010-1736-1>.
- [121] M.R. Lee, R.J. Lee, Y.W. Lin, C.M. Chen, B.H. Hwang, Gas-phase postderivatization following solid-phase microextraction for determining acidic herbicides in water, *Anal. Chem.* 70 (1998) 1963–1968, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac971153g>.
- [122] A.C. Dirtu, L. Roosens, T. Geens, A. Gheorghe, H. Neels, A. Covaci, Simultaneous determination of bisphenol A, triclosan, and tetrabromobisphenol A in human serum using solid-phase extraction and gas chromatography-electron capture negative-ionization mass spectrometry, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 391 (2008) 1175–1181, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-007-1807-9>.
- [123] F. Stilo, E. Liberto, S.E. Reichenbach, Q. Tao, C. Bicchì, C. Cordero, Untargeted and targeted fingerprinting of extra virgin olive oil volatiles by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography with mass spectrometry: challenges in long-term studies, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 67 (2019) 5289–5302, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b01661>.
- [124] T. Gröger, M. Schäffer, M. Pütz, B. Ahrens, K. Drew, M. Eschner, R. Zimmermann, Application of two-dimensional gas chromatography combined with pixel-based chemometric processing for the chemical profiling of illicit drug samples, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1200 (2008) 8–16, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2008.05.028>.
- [125] H. Mohammed Taha, R. Aalizadeh, N. Alygizakis, J.P. Antignac, H.P.H. Arp, R. Bade, N. Baker, L. Belova, L. Bijlsma, E.E. Bolton, W. Brack, A. Celma, W. L. Chen, T. Cheng, P. Chirsir, L. Cirka, L.A. D’Agostino, Y. Djoumbou Feunang, V. Dulió, S. Fischer, P. Gago-Ferrero, A. Galani, B. Geueke, N. Glowacka, J. Glüge, K. Groh, S. Grosse, P. Haglund, P.J. Hakkinen, S.E. Hale, F. Hernandez, E.M. L. Janssen, T. Jonkers, K. Kiefer, M. Kirchner, J. Koschorreck, M. Krauss, J. Krier, M.H. Lamoree, M. Letzel, T. Letzel, Q. Li, J. Little, Y. Liu, D.M. Lunderberg, J. W. Martin, A.D. McEachran, J.A. McLean, C. Meier, J. Meijer, F. Menger, C. Merino, J. Muncke, M. Muschket, M. Neumann, V. Neveu, K. Ng, H. Oberacher, J. O’Brien, P. Oswald, M. Oswaldova, J.A. Picache, C. Postigo, N. Ramirez, T. Reentsma, J. Renaud, P. Rostkowski, H. Rüdell, R.M. Salek, S. Samanipour, M. Scheringer, I. Schliebner, W. Schulz, T. Schulze, M. Sengl, B.A. Shoemaker, K. Sims, H. Singer, R.R. Singh, M. Sumaroh, P.A. Thiessen, K.V. Thomas, S. Torres, X. Trier, A.P. van Wezel, R.C.H. Vermeulen, J.J. Vlaanderen, P.C. von der Ohe, Z. Wang, A.J. Williams, E.L. Willighagen, D.S. Wishart, J. Zhang, N.S. Thomaidis, J. Hollender, J. Slobodnik, E.L. Schymanski, The NORMAN Suspect List Exchange (NORMAN-SLE): facilitating European and worldwide collaboration on suspect screening in high resolution mass spectrometry, *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 34 (2022) 1–26, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-022-00680-6>.
- [126] M.J. Hartnett, W.D. Watson, J.A. Janssen, J. Hua, J. Grossman, Q. Peng, P. Hartnett, K.A. Favela, Rapid screening of consumer products by GC×GC-HRT and machine learning assisted data processing, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jasm.s.3c00107>, 2023.
- [127] T.J. Trinklein, C.N. Cain, G.S. Ochoa, S. Schöneich, L. Mikaliunaite, R.E. Synovec, Recent advances in GC×GC and chemometrics to address emerging challenges in

- nontargeted analysis, *Anal. Chem.* 95 (2023) 264–286, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.2c04235>.
- [128] P.H. Stefanuto, A. Smolinska, J.F. Focant, Advanced chemometric and data handling tools for GC×GC-TOF-MS: application of chemometrics and related advanced data handling in chemical separations, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* 139 (2021) 116251, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2021.116251>.
- [129] F. Stilo, C. Cordero, C. Bicchi, D. Peroni, Q. Tao, S.E. Reichenbach, Chromatographic fingerprinting by template matching for data collected by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography, *JoVE* 2020 (2020) 1–20, <https://doi.org/10.3791/61529>.
- [130] S. Furbo, A.B. Hansen, T. Skov, J.H. Christensen, Pixel-based analysis of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatograms (color plots) of petroleum: a tutorial, *Anal. Chem.* 86 (2014) 7160–7170.
- [131] J.S. Lübeck, G.L. Alexandrino, J.H. Christensen, GC × GC-HRMS nontarget fingerprinting of organic micropollutants in urban freshwater sediments, *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 32 (2020) 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-020-00353-2>.
- [132] D. Zhang, X. Huang, F.E. Regnier, M. Zhang, Two-dimensional correlation optimized warping algorithm for aligning GC×GC-MS data, *Anal. Chem.* 80 (2008) 2664–2671, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac7024317>.
- [133] G. Tomasi, F. Savorani, S.B. Engelsen, Icoshift: an effective tool for the alignment of chromatographic data, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1218 (2011) 7832–7840, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2011.08.086>.
- [134] L.C. Marney, W. Christopher Siegler, B.A. Parsons, J.C. Hoggard, B.W. Wright, R. E. Synovec, Tile-based Fisher-ratio software for improved feature selection analysis of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography-time-of-flight mass spectrometry data, *Talanta* 115 (2013) 887–895, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2013.06.038>.
- [135] K.J. Johnson, R.E. Synovec, Pattern recognition of jet fuels: comprehensive GC × GC with ANOVA-based feature selection and principal component analysis, *Chemometr. Intell. Lab. Syst.* 60 (2002) 225–237, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7439\(01\)00198-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7439(01)00198-8).
- [136] B.A. Parsons, L.C. Marney, W.C. Siegler, J.C. Hoggard, B.W. Wright, R.E. Synovec, Tile-based Fisher ratio analysis of comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography time-of-flight mass spectrometry (GC × GC-TOFMS) data using a null distribution approach, *Anal. Chem.* 87 (2015) 3812–3819, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac504472s>.